

Identification of Cure Kinetic Parameters to Model Multiphysic Behavior of Thermoset Laminate Composite

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1. Context and objectives

Context

- Ain-T-Graal project funded by the DGAC (French Civil Aviation Authority)
- Responds to production speed requirements
- Studied piece → fuselage frame
- Part made entirely of composite **Complex geometry → curved shape / heterogeneous thickness**

Evolution of orders and deliveries of Airbus frame
Source Airbus

Aircraft fuselage

Project objectives

- Problematic : piece distortion (spring-back) in the end of the process
- Causes :
 - Formation of residual stress during the curing process
 - Interaction piece/tool
- Studied material:
 - Carbon fiber: IMA 12K
 - Thermoset epoxy resin: M21E/34%
 - Presence thermoplastic layers

- Development of a multi-physics numerical simulation
- Including 3 modulus for each physics
- **Focus on the implementation of the kinetic module and CSC characterization**

2. Cure kinetic module implementation

Cure Kinetic Modulus

- Resolution of degree of cure equation : α
- Resolution of Di Benedetto equation : T_g

Cure Kinetic Model

Kamal & Sourour model

- Goal : To calculate the degree of cure α
- Why : Well-known from the literature & easy to identify

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2\alpha^m)(\alpha_{max} - \alpha)^n$$

Di Benedetto Law

- Goal : Determine the evolution of the T_g during curing of the material

$$\frac{T_g - T_{g0}}{T_{g\infty} - T_{g0}} = \frac{\lambda\alpha}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha}$$

Protocol identification of KS Model

Equation to identify : $\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2\alpha^m)(\alpha_{max} - \alpha)^n$

1. Non-isothermal differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) test → Identify the total heat of cure ΔH_{total} and use it to calculate alpha $\alpha(t) = \frac{H(t)}{\Delta H_{total}}$
2. Isothermal DSC → Identify the maximum degree of cure α_{max} for each isothermal test
3. Plot polymerization rate $\frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ versus α → use curve fit Python module to identify parameters of KS model

Isotherm (°C)	K1 ($10^{-4}s^{-1}$)	K2 ($10^{-4}s^{-1}$)	m	n
160	1.079	2.499	0.6348	1.397
170	2.306	3.499	0.455	1.342
180	3.335	4.895	0.352	1.249
190	7.038	6.355	0.505	1.800
200	11.001	7.166	0.511	1.441

Protocol

1. Iso-thermal DSC test → To reach a maximum degree of cure for a given temperature
2. Dynamic (0°C → 300°C) on the same sample → Measure the new Tg for a given degree of cure
3. Plot the value of Tg versus degree of cure
4. Identification of the parameter λ

T_{g0} (°C)	$T_{g\infty}$ (°C)	λ
-3	240	0.716

3. Thermal & Shrinkage coefficient characterisation

- Image correlation with 2 cameras
- Unidirectional sample under thermal stress
- Creating random speckles
- Create strain field from temporal matching of these speckles

Cameras

Displacement field and strain on 3D profile

Cooling

Oven

Thermal loading

Fibers direction

CET characterization

Measure on a cured sample

— Strain ϵ_{yy} - - - Strain ϵ_{xx} - - - Linear regression

eYY strain field

eXX strain field

Identification
 $CTE_{xx} \rightarrow \text{Assumed } 0e^{-6} K^{-1}$
 $CTE_{yy} \rightarrow 30e^{-6} K^{-1}$

CSC characterization

- Test on uncured UD material
- Iso-thermal 170°C test → To isolate chemical strain from thermally induced strains
- **Focus on strain after the gel point**

CSC _{xx}	CSC _{yy} before gel	CSC _{xx} after gel
Negligible	0%	-0.74%

4. Conclusion et perspectives

Industrial production issues

- Geometric distortion of parts at the end of the process

Digital prediction tool design

- Multi-physics model (mechanical, thermal, chemical)
- Coupling between the different modules

Cure Kinetic module implementation

- Kamal & Sourour Model identification $\rightarrow \alpha$
- Di Benedetto curve $\rightarrow T_g(\alpha)$

CSC characterization

- Use of the DIC for characterised the CSC coefficients
- Simple method applied directly to UD material

Ongoing work

- Correlation with lab demonstrator
- Apply the numerical model to the structure studied

Thank you for your attention

